

Assessment of Impervious Surface Growth in the Mula-mutha Watershed in Maharashtra

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ABSTRACT: *The Mula-Mutha watershed is located in the western Maharashtra which nests Pune urban agglomeration at its central part. For the assessment of impervious surface growth of this watershed, satellite images of 1989 and 2008 have been used. An integrated application of remote sensing techniques using Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and Geographic Information System (GIS) has been carried out to identify the amount of impervious surface and its variations. The Impervious surface analysis reveals that there has been almost three-fold increase of the built up area under very high impervious class representing the Pune city and its surroundings between 1989 and 2008. The entire scenario is indicating the requirement of immediate remediation through pollutant mitigation and resource restoration in those areas.*

Keywords : *impervious surface, watershed, normalized difference vegetation index, built up area.*

Introduction

For the last couple of decades or so, large scale human activities have brought about an enormous change on the Earth's surface. The effects of urbanization and industrialization are clearly noticeable, especially in the urban areas. But their indirect influences can be observed in the adjacent areas of the city too. Land-use changes occur at many places and it is observed that vegetation and barren land have changed into non-evaporating and non-transpiring impervious concrete surfaces. Natural land surface cover has been removed continuously and this has led to a simultaneous increase in impervious surface cover. It not only hampers the natural eco-system, but also has long term effects on the climate, natural resources, economy and culture of the surrounding areas.

The impervious surfaces have been increasing rapidly and those are mainly associated with the cities and heavily populated areas. United Nations (2002) has projected doubling of the global urban population by 2030. The study of spatio-temporal change in impervious surfaces would facilitate the understanding of a watershed containing a big urban environment and its relationship with urbanization and industrialization.

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Mapping of Impervious Surface: Impervious surface mapping is an attempt to track the pattern of land use changes. Impervious surfaces are defined as any surface which does not allow water to infiltrate and are primarily associated with transportation (streets, highways, parking lots and sidewalks) and building rooftops. Imperviousness directly affects the amount of runoff to streams and lakes and is related to non-point source pollution and water quality of surrounding water bodies. The amount of impervious surface in a landscape is an indicator of environmental quality (Arnold and Gibbons, 1996). In a natural landscape, the maximum amount of runoff occurs after the beginning of a storm. As impervious surface area increases, the storm water coming off of them increases velocity, quantity, temperature, and pollution load. Any one of these attributes contributes to the degradation of natural hydrology and water quality. Noticeable degradation of water bodies begins when the watershed reaches 10-20 percent imperviousness. Quantifying and analyzing impervious surfaces is an important step in determining the current condition of a watershed. It can serve as a key ingredient to carry out further research for determining land use planning implications and directing future decision-making processes for ecologically sensitive zones. A general relationship showing the health status of a watershed decreasing with increasing impervious coverage was given by Schuler in 1994 (fig. 1). He stated that the health of a watershed can be categorized as protected, impacted and degraded, depending upon the percentage of impervious surface available.

Fig. 1 Relationship of imperviousness to the health status of the area
(Modified from Schuler, 1994)

Fig. 2 Location Map of the Study Area

He identified certain threshold values in order to define the health status of the watershed. If the region has less than 10 percent of impervious surface then it is treated as protected, if it is from 10 percent to 25 percent then it is treated as impacted and above 25 percent of impervious surface indicates a degraded state. This categorization is followed by almost the entire scientific community working on the studies related to imperviousness. The results of the impervious surface analysis can be used to guide planning emphasis within each local area. For areas in the lower impervious zone, emphasis should be placed in preventive measures that retain existing natural systems, using techniques like open space planning and stream buffers.

The main aim of the study is to bring about spatio-temporal variations in impervious surfaces of the Mula-Mutha watershed during the period of 1989-2008. To fulfill this, following objectives have been outlined:

- To extract impervious surfaces from satellite data.
- To evaluate the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and impervious surface within the watershed for the study period.

Fig. 3. Flow-chart showing the methodology adopted for the study.

Source : Prepared by the authors

Study Area: The area under consideration is Mula-Mutha watershed (18°18'N - 18°44'N, 73°20'E - 74°20'E) which includes Pune city, which is rapidly growing in terms of the urban space. The location of the watershed with reference to India and Maharashtra is shown in the figure-2. Mula and Mutha rivers originate from Sahyadri ranges lying in the west of the watershed and they are the tributaries of the Bhima River. The region lies in the Deccan trap volcanic province. Mula and Mutha rivers and all their tributaries are of seasonal type. They receive water from the monsoon rainfall. The climate of the watershed is dry but invigorating. The area lies in the rain shadow zone of the Western Ghats. Semi-arid climate with monsoon rainfall is the common characteristic of the region.

Methodology

Data Acquisition and Preprocessing: For the present work, Landsat 4 TM and IRS P6 LISS III images were used (table 1). The geometric correction of Landsat 4 TM (1989) image was done by using ERDAS Imagine 9.2 software. The IRS P6 LISS III (2008) image acquired from National Remote Sensing Centre (NRSC), Hyderabad had already been corrected geometrically. For radiometric and atmospheric correction of the images of 1989 and 2008, the models built in ERDAS imagine 9.1 by Dhorde and Wakhare (2008) was employed.

TABLE-1 : Satellite Data used for the Study

Satellite	Sensor	Date
IRS P6	LISS III	14 th February, 2008
LANDSAT	4 TM	11 th February, 1989

Source : Prepared by the authors

Reprojection and Resampling: The images were reprojected to Geographic Latitude/Longitude with the WGS 84 spheroid and datum. IRS P6 LISS III image of 2008 had a spatial resolution of 23.5 meter whereas the resolution of Landsat 4 TM 1989 image was 30 meter. In order to make both these images comparable the IRS image was resampled and brought down to 30m resolution. This process can be attempted in both ArcGIS as well as ERDAS imagine softwares.

Image Enhancement: Simple enhancement techniques like contrast-stretch, histogram equalization etc. were performed for visual interpretation.

Obtaining Subset for the Area of Interest: The area of interest (AOI) was obtained with the help of a vector layer prepared in the same projection as that of the images. This AOI is the boundary of the Mula-Mutha watershed. Data subsetting was done for the images of Landsat 4 TM and IRS P6 LISS III. These subsets were further employed for obtaining desired parameters.

Calculation of Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI): The NDVI calculation was done in ERDAS imagine by running the indices option. Normalized difference vegetation index uses

the combination of band 3 (0.63-0.69 μm) i.e. red band and band 4 (0.76-0.90 μm) i.e. near infrared band for Landsat 4 TM image. NDVI is representative of plant assimilation condition and its photosynthetic apparatus capacity and biomass concentration (Groten, 1993). NDVI is representative of plant photosynthetic efficiency. It is time varying due to the changes in meteorological and environmental parameters. Healthy vegetation will have a high NDVI value. Bare soil and rock reflect similar levels of near-infrared and red and so will have NDVI values near zero. Clouds, water, and snow are the opposite of vegetation in that they reflect more visible energy than infrared energy, and so they yield negative NDVI values. NDVI for Landsat TM, ETM+ and IRS LISS III, PAN images is calculated by the following equation:

$$\text{NDVI} = \frac{(\text{Near Infra Red} - \text{Red})}{(\text{Near Infra Red} + \text{Red})} = \frac{\text{NIR} - \text{R}}{\text{NIR} + \text{R}}$$

Extraction of NDVI values: The NDVI provides a standardized method for comparing vegetation greenness between the satellite imageries (Wang et al., 2005). In this research, cells with low NDVI values can be recognized as low greenness values which correspond to the cells of potential impervious characteristics. This method was proposed in 1973 by Rouse et al. as a simple algorithm to process data. It locates the arrangement pattern of vegetation in the Great Plains and remains as the most used index to detect live green plant covers in the satellite data.

Retrieval of Impervious Surface for Landsat 4 TM and IRS LISS III Images: Out of a number of methods elaborated in literature and employed in the extraction of Impervious Surface Area (ISA), a method relying upon the basic factor of vegetation cover was selected for the extraction of impervious surface cover for the concerned watershed. An integrated application of satellite remote sensing techniques using Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and Geographic Information System (GIS) is carried out to estimate the amount of impervious surface and their variation for the time period spanning twenty years (1989-2008). Here impervious surface is derived using the classified land use image and the NDVI image. The NDVI image obtained is further used to categorize the levels of imperviousness and then employed to generate the percentage of ISA per category of NDVI. The table 2 below is showing Translation of NDVI range into imperviousness range.

Interestingly, it is observed that the values for water and developed areas (i.e. impervious surface zones) have coincided with each other. So water might have got classified as an impervious layer in addition to the built up structures. Thus, a bias might have been introduced in the analysis part. So the next task involved was to mask out water from the NDVI rasters.

Water Masking: For doing water masking ArcGIS spatial analysis capabilities are used. In this process, all other land use classes except the water bodies have been eliminated. The table given below (table 3) illustrates how the water class was separated from the NDVI integer raster using the combine function.

Combining NDVI integer and Water class: Combining is done by the ArcGIS software which works only with the NDVI integer values. So, it was necessary to convert the decimal NDVI values into the integer values. This conversion was performed in the ERDAS Model builder wherein a simple model was built to convert NDVI decimal values to NDVI integer values. For the combine function, water masked and NDVI images were used. Interestingly, the nature of the NDVI raster of having higher values for vegetation and lower values for impervious area reversed after it was combined with the water raster. The tables below (table 4a and 4b) are showing that.

TABLE-4a : Differences between NDVI Integer raster and Combine raster for 1989

NDVI Interpretation	NDVI Integer Value	ArcGIS Combine value	Combine Interpretation
Impervious	-100	1	Impervious
	To	To	
Vegetation	100	365	Vegetation

Source : Prepared by the authors

Table-4b : Differences between NDVI Integer raster and Combine raster for 2008

NDVI Interpretation	NDVI Integer Value	ArcGIS Combine value	Combine Interpretation
Impervious	-65	1	Impervious
	To	To	
Vegetation	35	142	Vegetation

Source : Prepared by the authors

After combining, break-up values were obtained for 1989 and 2008 combined images on the basis of natural break method by using ArcGIS and these values are the indicators of imperviousness of different parts of the watershed.

Imperviousness Indices: Deriving impervious surface area in square kilometer and percentage was the final goal of the present study. For this the break-up values obtained were used to find the area under each class and finally to compute the per cent imperviousness. The method given by Sleavin (1999) and Prisløe et al. (2000) was adopted for the computation. Accordingly the impervious surface area within each class is calculated as:

$$IS_{\text{coefficient}} = \frac{NDVI_{\text{class}}_{\text{Area}}}{NDVI_{\text{class}}_{\text{Area}}}$$

$NDVI_{class}^{IS_{area}}$ is the total area of impervious surface for a specific NDVI combine class.

$NDVI_{class}^{Area}$ is the total area for the same NDVI combine class.

With this method, NDVI data are converted to a GIS polygon format and overlaid on impervious surface data extracted from the supervised classified image. This process was repeated for each land use type for each NDVI combine class, resulting in a set of regionally calibrated impervious surface coefficients.

Results and Discussion

Impervious Surface Area for 1989: NDVI values for the 1989 image ranges from -1 to +1. From these values, NDVI integer values were extracted which ranged from -100 to +100 (Fig. 4). Higher NDVI values indicated highly vegetative areas whereas lower values corresponded with the built up surfaces.

By combining the NDVI integer and water raster (Fig. 5) the combine image for 1989 was obtained. The combined image took the values ranging from 1 to 365. The combined image is shown in the fig. 6. From this image, four specific break up values were assigned on the basis of their potential imperviousness viz. 1 to 30 (Moderately Impervious Surface), 30-45 (High Impervious Surface), 45-60 (Very High Impervious Surface) and above 60 (Low Impervious Surface).

From the combined image it was found that moderately impervious surfaces are in the western side of the watershed near the big reservoirs indicating the vegetative parts. High impervious surface dominated most parts of the image and mainly included the barren land. Very high impervious layers can be observed in a scattered manner. Low impervious surfaces can be found at or near the water bodies.

Built up class was extracted from the supervised classified image of 1989 (fig. 7). The percentage of built up for every combined break up class is calculated and the results are shown in the table 5.

As observed from the given table, very high impervious class contains almost 15 percent built up area. The highest built up area percentage is found in high impervious class (15.5 percent).

Table-5 : Impervious Surface Area (ISA) Calculation, 1989

Break up class	Built up area (in sq.km)	Total area (in sq.km)	IS coefficient	ISA percent
Very High Impervious	83.30	562.60	0.1480	14.80
High Impervious	76.40	493.57	0.1547	15.47
Moderately Impervious	192.54	1385.79	0.1389	13.89
Low Impervious	25.98	309.46	0.0839	8.39

Source : Prepared by the authors from satellite data

Fig. 4 NDVI Integer Image, 1989

Fig. 5 Water Raster, 1989

Fig. 6 Combined Image, 1989

Fig. 7 Built up Area, 1989

Whereas, the moderate impervious class comprises more area than any other class and possessing almost 14 percent built up area. As expected, the low impervious class contains the lowest percentage built up area (8 percent).

Here a discrepancy can be noticed. Normally, very high impervious class (Class I) is expected to have the highest span of built up area. However, maximum proportion of built up area is found in the high impervious surface class (Class II). It is observed that areas under Class I appear to be distributed in a scattered pattern as opposed to an idealistic clustering one. There is no compactness identified in this class. So, built up areas occur in a scattered manner in this class. Low impervious class unexpectedly has a significant proportion of built up area, indicating occurrence of man-made structures around the water bodies.

It is evident from these results that there is less concentration of impervious layers even in the higher impervious classes. This indicates that Pune city didn't experience an enormous amount of constructional activities before 1989.

Impervious Surface Area for 2008: NDVI values for the 2008 image ranges from -0.65 to +0.35. From these values, NDVI integer values were extracted which ranged from -65 to +35 (Fig. 8). After extracting the NDVI integer, again the water masking was carried out.

The combined image values ranged from 1 to 142 (Fig. 10). From this image, four specific break up classes were assigned again on the basis of their potential imperviousness viz. 1 to 15 (Moderately Impervious Surface), 15-27 (High Impervious Surface), 27-50 (Very High Impervious Surface) and above 50 (Low Impervious Surface).

As compared to the 1989 combined image, the distribution of moderately impervious surfaces were the same in the western side of the watershed, but in the downstream it has increased considerably. High impervious surface again dominated a major part of the watershed. Very high impervious layers have been found in a compact manner, especially in the middle part where Pune city is situated. Occurrence of low impervious surfaces remained more or less unchanged.

The percentage of built up for every combined break up class is calculated and the results are shown in the table-6. As indicated in the table, very high impervious class contains 43.4 percent built up area. 16.4 percent impervious surface area percentage is found in high impervious class. The moderate impervious class comprises of only 9 percent built up Area. Low impervious class contains the most negligible percentage built up area 0.5 percent.

Here, expectedly the very high impervious class contains the highest percentage built up area. As compared with the situation in 1989, the built up percentage under very high impervious class has increased strikingly with the increase in built up area. The built up percentage in high impervious layer is also greater than before. The moderate impervious class contains lower impervious surface percentage than 1989. A significant decrease in built up percentage is marked in the low impervious class with very less area under built up.

Fig. 8 NDVI Integer Image, 2008

Fig. 9 Water Raster, 2008

Fig. 10 Combined Image, 2008

Fig. 11 Built up Area, 2008

Table-6 : Impervious Surface Area (ISA) Calculation, 1989

Break up class	Built up area (in sq.km)	Total area (in sq.km)	IS coefficient	ISA percent
Very High Impervious	155.66	358.35	0.4344	43.44
High Impervious	228.54	1393.90	0.1640	16.40
Moderately Impervious	102.38	1126.10	0.090	9.09
Low Impervious	0.67	145.00	0.0046	0.46

Source : Prepared by the authors from satellite data

These results show that the constructional activities have increased rapidly in the last two decades in the watershed. The city and its surroundings have experienced a large scale change that might have affected the residents.

Impacts of Occurrence of Impervious Surfaces: The imperviousness in different areas of the watershed can be identified and specific actions can be taken on the basis of their vulnerability. The main reason behind the imperviousness of an area is the built up surface developed there. So more percentage area under built up indicates more impermeability as far as the impact is concerned. According to Schuler (1994), a watershed is:

- Protected - at 10 percent or less impervious surface area,
- Impacted - at 10 percent-25 percent impervious surface area and
- Degraded - at greater than 25 percent impervious surface area.

By observing fig. 12a, we can assess the impact of the impervious surfaces in 1989. It can be recognized that the watershed is largely impacted with 10 percent-25 percent areas under impervious surface where preventive planning measure should be accompanied with a focus on site design considerations that reduces runoff and imperviousness. Very less amount of area is found under protected zone with less than 10 percent or less impervious surface area where emphasis should be placed in preventive measures that retain existing natural systems, using techniques like open space planning and stream buffers. No area is found under degraded zone in 1989.

Fig. 12b is showing the impact of increasing impervious surfaces in 2008. It is clearly evident from the image that the degraded areas with more than 25 percent impervious surface occur in Pune city located in the central part of the watershed and Pimpri-Chindhwad city in its north-west. For this zone, the remediation through pollutant mitigation and resource restoration should be given importance. The other areas having the built up units are under the impacted zone with almost no occurrence of the protected zone. So, it can be clearly stated that for the last 20 years, built up areas have been increasing quite rapidly in and around the city region. Therefore the changing condition of the watershed under concern is quite evident.

Fig. 12a Impervious Surface Area, 1989

Fig. 12b. Impervious Surface Area, 2008

Summary and Conclusion

The study undertaken has helped to understand changes in impervious surfaces in the Mula-Mutha watershed over the last two decades. The study also highlights the expansion of Pune city and surroundings over the same period. Impervious surface mapping is an attempt to track the pattern of land use changes. The increasing amount of impervious surfaces indicates the expansion of urban areas with a number of industrial and residential projects.

Major Findings of the Study:

- Very high impervious class contains almost 15 percent built up area in 1989; whereas, in 2008, 43.4 percent built up area is found in the very high impervious class. So there is almost three times increase in the built up area under this class in the last two decades.
- The built up percentage under the high impervious class has increased slightly, only about 1 percent. These areas are mostly found in the fringes of the city.
- In 1989, most of the areas in the watershed were impacted with 10 percent-25 percent areas under impervious surface. No area was found in the degraded zone in 1989 image. The occurrence of protected area is also very less.
- In 2008, a significant proportion of the impacted area has transformed into the degraded area with more than 25 percent of the impervious surface cover. In addition to this, certain new areas, which have been developed in the past two decades, are in the degraded zone. All the degraded areas are found in and around the Pune city and Pimpri-Chinchwad indicating rapid constructional activities in these areas in the recent past. The areas under the protected class are negligible in 2008.

Conclusion

It has been noticed that almost three times increase in the built up area has occurred in the Pune and Pimpri-Chinchwad cities. Nowadays, impervious surface is considered as an indicator of environmental fitness. In the Mula-Mutha Watershed, for the last two decades, a lot of changes have occurred as far as the impervious surface coverage is concerned. An appreciable proportion of these built up units is found in the degraded areas with more than 25 percent built up surfaces have been set up in those areas. Apart from these areas there are also some fringe areas which can be pointed out as impacted areas. So, attention should be given to those sites also where new constructions have been going on.

In the Mula-Mutha Watershed, due to the presence of Pune and Pimpri-Chinchwad cities, the developmental activities cannot be stopped. But to nullify the effects of the hazardous incidents, some immediate actions could be taken like designing constructions that reduce runoff and imperviousness etc. Optimum use of resources should be given importance. Sustainable development should be encouraged which will give people a chance to use the existing resources in the long term basis without obstructing the present use of the resources.

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